

Thiazolidinones as Potential Antibacterial Compound. Part—I

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2-Aryl-3-(3-uridophenyl)-4-thiazolidinones (II) have been prepared from the reaction of thioglycolic acid with azomethines in dry benzene. The azomethines have been prepared by condensation of different aromatic aldehyde with *m*-urido aniline. The compounds (II) show good antibacterial activity when tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by nutrient agar pour plate method.

THIAZOLIDINONES have been found to exhibit antitubercular activity¹. The nucleus is also active as hypnotic², anaesthetic³ and antifungal⁴. Phenyl urea derivatives show central myorelaxant effect⁵, motor inordinating activity, anticorazol⁶ and anticonvulsive⁷⁻¹⁰ activities.

For preparation of 4-thiazolidinones¹¹ of the type (II), the Schiff's¹² bases of 3-aminophenyl urea have been prepared with different aromatic aldehyde and condensed with thioglycolic acid in dry benzene. When tested, these compounds (II) showed antibacterial activity by disk diffusion method.

IR spectra of the title compounds were taken on a Beckmann spectrophotometer. The strong bands at 1750 cm⁻¹, 1760 cm⁻¹ were characteristic carbonyl stretching frequency for thiazolidinone ring system.

Experimental

To the solution of aldehyde (0.01 M) in ethanol (50 ml; 95%) was added *m*-urido aniline (0.01 M) in ethanol (50 ml; 95%). The contents were heated to reflux for 2 hr, cooled and worked out to get the corresponding Schiff's base: -C₆H₄, 115°; -2-OH-C₆H₄, 208°; -2-OH-5-Br-C₆H₃, 222°; 2-OH-3,5-diBr-C₆H₃, 202°; 4-OCH₃-C₆H₄, 160°; 4-N-(CH₃)₂-C₆H₄, 110°; CH-CH₃-C₆H₅, 105°; -3-OH-C₆H₄, 165°; -3-Cl-C₆H₄, 115°; -4-Cl-C₆H₄, 150°; -3NO₂, 152°; -4-NO₂, 163°; 4-OH-3-OCH₃-C₆H₃, 158°; -4-OH-C₆H₄, 180°.

Azomethine (0.01 M), dry benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.012 M) were heated to reflux (~ 25 hr), using a Dean and Stark water separator. The solvent was removed and the residue was treated with NaHCO₃ solution and filtered. The thiazolidinones were crystallised from ethanol (95%), (yield: 45%): -C₆H₄, 285°; -2.OH.C₆H₄, 301°; -2.OH.5 Br-C₆H₃, 280°; -2.OH 3,5-diBr C₆H₃, 248°; -4.OCH₃.C₆H₄, 245°; 4-N-(CH₃)₂ C₆H₄, 130°; -CH=CH.C₆H₅, 255°; -3OH.C₆H₄, 260°; -3.Cl.C₆H₄, 100°; 4.Cl.C₆H₄, 280°;

-3NO₂.C₆H₄, 238°; -4NO₂.C₆H₄, 216°; -4.OH.3-OCH₃-C₆H₃, 190°; -4-OH.C₆H₄, 278°.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds (II) were tested for antibacterial activities by nutrient agar pour plate method in dimethyl formamide and were found active against *E.coli* and *S.aureus* in various concentration.

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TABLE I—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE THIAZOLIDINONE OF THE TYPE

Sl. No.	R	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₄	+	-
2.	-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	++	++
3.	2-OH.5-Br-C ₆ H ₃	++	+
4.	2-OH-3,5-di-Br-C ₆ H ₃	++	++
5.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	+	-
6.	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	-	-
7.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	-	-
8.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	+	-
9.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	+	-
10.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	+	+
11.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	+	+
12.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	+	+
13.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	+	+
14.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	+

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

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